

CREATIVE APPROACH TO MUSIC LESSONS IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. *Aesthetic education is the process of forming the skills of correct understanding and acceptance of existence and art in young people, instilling aesthetic feelings, tastes and views in them, developing the need and abilities of students to participate in the creation of beauty.*

Keywords: *education, beauty, preschool educational organization, music.*

In a preschool educational organization, the head of music is a pedagogue with a narrow specialty who organizes music lessons through musical education of preschool age. It serves to develop children's musical taste and initial musical literacy and to raise their musical ability to the level of ability. The music director conducts group and individual activities with the children. Based on the work schedule approved by the director, he carries out important tasks such as group training, cooperation with pedagogues, individual work with children, spiritual and entertainment hours, organization of children's holiday mornings. In order No. 173 of the Ministry of Preschool Education on the approval of qualification descriptions of the main positions of preschool education workers, the job duties of the music director are described as follows:

Each music director must follow the programs developed by the Ministry of Pre-School Education and the state standard of preschool education. That is, attention is focused on developing the basic competencies of the child specified in the state program, organizing activities taking into account the child's age characteristics, determining the educational process based on weekly and monthly topics according to thematic planning.

During each academic year, the head of music is expected to present the results of his new methodical works and research in the form of an open training or seminar to the pedagogues and management team, as well as to the members of the supervisory board. In order to popularize advanced pedagogical practices, the work of a music director with many years of experience is studied through open classes and seminars.

While the music director works individually with children with low learning and abilities, he has to work in cooperation with their parents. It is necessary to organize continuous cooperation in order to repeat the assigned tasks at home and increase the enthusiasm of parents for the child's mastery. The music leader organizes cooperation with the teacher or teacher's assistant of the group in which he is conducting music lessons in order to master the taught songs or rhythmic movements. In order to consolidate the work taught in the short-term music lessons, educators repeat the words of this song in the free activities of the children's daily routine. This is an effective way to organize targeted cooperation.

The music director should carry out the educational activities scheduled at the beginning of the academic year on time, show enthusiasm in holding holidays and entertainment days in pre-school educational organizations, and keep the music hall in a comfortable condition with educational and educational equipment for children. conducts organizational work such as decoration. Any music director who enjoys his work, who finds joy in working with children,

performs such tasks diligently.

Having a good knowledge of the child's development indicators in terms of age, the pedagogue should organize music lessons with them by using different types of musical activities. Five main types of musical activity are identified as being used by the music director. Listening and perception of music, singing, musical rhythmic movements, accompaniment on children's musical instruments and music literacy.

First of all, children learn music individually and collectively through singing and accompanying musical instruments. Children demonstrate their abilities in front of the team, develop creative and self-competencies that are formed in them. Performing group singing and musical rhythmic games helps to eliminate their shyness and human qualities, and at the same time, helps to form their communicative competence. Since the activity of teaching musical instruments is a complex process, it requires individual work with the child. Based on the instructions of the music director, the child should be able to hold the instrument correctly, the position of standing, if it is an instrument that requires sitting, the position of sitting, the ways of sounding the instrument, the initial he has to perform exercises aimed at forming musical literacy and the ability to feel the rhythm. However, if the pedagogue conducts the teaching of musical instruments in the form of an ensemble, he will teach the children to listen to each other's performances and play in unison if they follow the instructions of the music director. At the same time, it gives students the opportunity to see each other's shortcomings and correct them. Taking these aspects into account, the music director should develop the child's creative abilities by organizing individual and group activities.

Every child has a different level of ability and talent. In addition, the family environment also affects their character and personal qualities. Some students are cheerful, energetic and enterprising, while others are reserved, modest and shy. But such qualities do not determine the level of ability of a child under the age of 3-7. The initial sign of ability is talent, and for its development, a creative environment is needed first of all. The creative environment is created by parents in the family and pedagogues in preschool educational organizations. It can be seen that a creative environment and the support of pedagogues are very important for bringing out the abilities hidden under the shyness of some children. As the music leader works with children in a creative approach to the organization of his work, he should pay special attention to these aspects and define his work plan. Depending on the level of opportunities, he will determine the plan for additional work with children, and individual work with children with low mastery. In addition, if the child has a physical and mental defect, a plan is drawn up in cooperation with pedagogues of narrow specialization, and methodical work is carried out together to improve the health of such children.

It is one of the job duties of every pedagogue to analyze the various age characteristics of the child, to observe whether the pre-school education and upbringing meet the state standards or not. The educator pedagogue and specialist pedagogues are responsible for monitoring and analyzing the changes and mastery levels of each child. If there are changes in the level of development of children, it is necessary to carry out final observations and control the planning and implementation of individual work.

Based on the thematic planning established in the state curriculum, educators should organize thematic songs and musical games for children in cooperation with music leaders. The teacher pedagogues and their assistants should be the assistants of the music director in the group

music lessons, they should call the children to order and help them to focus on the lesson, perform the movements and sing the songs.

Aesthetic education is the process of forming the skills of correct understanding and acceptance of existence and art in young people, instilling aesthetic feelings, tastes and views in them, developing the need and abilities of students to participate in the creation of beauty.

Children's development is analyzed during music lessons. Through holidays and various musical evenings, collective and individual performances of children are observed, and students with higher musical ability and hearing ability compared to their peers are distinguished. They are given additional tasks and focus on further developing their musical hearing. Parents of gifted children are given advice on how to help their child develop their talent and direct them to music careers in the future.

Preschool educational organizations are full of musical evenings, spiritual events, entertainment hours, holiday mornings. Educators and pedagogues of all narrow specialties cooperate in organizing holidays. The cycle of holiday mornings will be prepared separately for each group. At the beginning of the year, the time and procedure are planned and approved by the director of the organization. A program consisting of songs and collective performances is developed with children through music lessons or holiday morning scenarios. It is necessary to follow the requirements and time standards for holding separate holidays for each group. Taking into account the attention and physical ability of children, it is necessary to work with them and provide various support. The time for celebrations for children of the small group (3-4) is 15-20 minutes, for children of the middle group (4-5) 25-30 minutes, for children of the senior group (5-6) 30-35 minutes, 35-40 minutes for school preparatory group (6-7) children.

In addition, sound amplifiers are widely used when pedagogues are engaged in activities with children. Of course, there is nothing wrong with that. Loudspeakers are very necessary for pedagogues in activities such as listening and understanding of music, "musical orchestra", performing musical didactic games and musical-rhythmic movements to music, physical education training. However, there are cases where the children's hearing is adversely affected by playing music at high volume, as well as by choosing to play very noisy and low-quality music. All pedagogues in the preschool educational organization are responsible for the child's spiritual growth and enjoyment of the beautiful magic of music.

First of all, preschool educational organization is a place of education and morals. Inculcating the moral standards of our national values in children will help them to understand black and white. By listening to our national music, tunes performed on Uzbek folk instruments, and placing quality musical products in their minds, we are able to form the musical aesthetic taste of children. In children, the manners of selective listening to music, listening and performance culture grow and develop.

While working in a preschool educational organization, the music director must adhere to the collective agreement. In the course of work, Maktabacha should meet the internal rules of the PEO and interact with pedagogues through a friendly and creative environment, while fulfilling the tasks provided for by the orders of the Ministry of Education.

The pedagogues of the preschool educational organization provide all-round protection of the child. As much work and protection is necessary for a new sprout to grow properly, it is necessary to protect it from various factors for the mental, spiritual and physical development of a human child.

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